

envision

D7.3 DRAFT REPORT ON DISSEMINATION ACTIVITIES

Project: Monitoring of Environmental Practices for Sustainable
Agriculture Supported by Earth Observation

Acronym: ENVISION

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Executive Summary

This deliverable reports on dissemination and communication activities performed in the frames of WP7 of ENVISION project from March 2022 to the end of May 2023.

It summarizes the achievements of the second half of the project and outlines the strategy plan and measures to communicate and disseminate the activities and results in the last months of the project, which will focus more on the commercial activities.

ENVISION project implementation follows the plan of activities as described in deliverable D7.1 Dissemination and Communication plan (M4). The structure of this document is an updated version of the D7.2 Intermediate report of dissemination activities (M18).

1 Introduction

Dissemination and communication activities are vital throughout the entire lifetime of the project to guarantee the success of the project.

This deliverable provides an intermediate report on the ENVISION dissemination activities. All partners regularly report their activities and achievements through the form prepared on the JotForm: <https://form.jotform.com/210193573145048>

This form helps all the partners for easy reporting and gives WP7 leader a clear view of dissemination and communication activities that have been done. In this deliverable, we use the short names of project partners, and for this purpose, the table with project partners is listed below.

Every partner in the ENVISION consortium acts directly or indirectly as a communication actor by boosting news via social media channels, producing text content to enhance the website, providing insights through targeted newsletter articles, developing liaisons with other projects, etc.

Table 1: Project Partners

No	Name	Short name	Country
1	DRAXIS ENVIRONMENTAL S.A.	DRXS	Greece
2	NATIONAL OBSERVATORY OF ATHENS	NOA	Greece
3	NATIONAL PAYING AGENCY	NPA	Lithuania
4	VLAAMSE GEWEST	LV	Belgium
5	ORGANISMOS AGROTIKON PLIROMON	CAPO	Cyprus
6	DOO ORGANIC CONTROL SYSTEM SUBOTICA	OCS	Serbia
7	EIGEN VERMOGEN VAN HET INSTITUT VOOR LANDBOUW – EN VISSERIJONDERZOEK	EV ILVO	Belgium
8	LINKING ENVIRONMENT AND FARMING LBG	LEAF	United Kingdom
9	THE UNIVERSITY OF READING	URDG	United Kingdom
10	ITC – INOVACIJSKO TEHNOLOŠKI GROZD MURSKA SOBOTA	ITC	Slovenia
11	ETAM ANONYMH ETAIREIA SYMBOYLEYTIKON KAI MELEHTIKON YPIRESION	ETAM	Greece
12	INOSENS DOO NOVI SAD	INOS	Serbia
13	AGRO APPS I.K.E.	AgroApps	Greece

2 Dissemination and communication tools and activities

During the period from the 1st March 2022 until the end of May 2023, several activities have been performed with a positive impact on the target audience. This section presents in detail all the dissemination and communication activities performed for this reporting period. WP7 focuses its efforts on implementing a priority-developed communication and dissemination strategy.

All consortium members share their communication and dissemination activities, news announcements, and additional material (event pictures, presentations, etc.) with the WP7 leader and can get instant support.

The main WP7 objectives were the following:

- Regularly updating ENVISION website
- Regularly publishing posts on ENVISION social channels
- Monitoring the project website and social media accounts
- Publishing newsletters
- Regularly meeting with a different audience
- Participating in different external events and conferences at the national and European level
- Organizing project events to raise visibility for the project
- Publishing articles in national, regional, and European press
- Scientific and technical publications
- Coordinating partners for all these activities for a better and stronger involvement in dissemination and promotional activities

2.1 ENVISION website

The ENVISION website (<https://envision-h2020.eu/>) has been running since the beginning of the project and is regularly updated by the webmaster with input from all partners.

In May 2023, we started with the re-structure of the ENVISION website through the home page. We will continue with the redesign to be tailored to the commercial offering of the project. A potential user/customer should arrive at a place where the offering of the project is immediately visible. A short video was prepared and added on the websites main page showcasing how the ENVISION platform is working.

Other main website features/sections are staying the same:

- About: providing more information about the project, data and products, services, business cases and target audience.
- News & Events: contains recent news, published newsletters, events and media hub.
- Networking: ENVISION is networking with other projects related to Earth Observation which are listed under this tab.
- Deliverables: Public deliverables are uploaded and marked in green.

- Partners: All project partners are listed with their logo. When clicks on their logo, and the link leads you to their website.
- Newsletter Signup: signup form for the project’s newsletter
- The disclaimer, EU logo, and contact details at the bottom part of each section can be found.
- The Privacy Policy and the Terms and Conditions have also been included in the ENVISION website, which is a set of general rules and policies governing the visitors’ use of the website.

Figure 1: The ENVISION home page before

Figure 2: The ENVISION home page after the first reconstruction

2.1.1 Website measurements

Website traffic is monitored using WP (Word Press) Statistics and Google Analytics installed at the beginning of the project. WP Statistics is a user-friendly tool for understanding our website's traffic and user data. It provides detailed information about the browser, search engine, and most popular content (categorized by tags, categories, and authors) of our website's visitors.

Data are collected monthly and provide data on user interactions with the site. For a better overview, the data are provided in the table below.

Table 2: Number of visitors and page views

C1: Number of visits to the project website		
Date	Visitors	Page Views
29/1/2021	116	9
28/2/2021	204	373
31/3/2021	227	374
30/4/2021	161	291
31/5/2021	184	379
30/6/2021	204	413
31/7/2021	327	273
31/8/2021	626	376
30/9/2021	350	289
31/10/2021	777	1315
30/11/2021	903	1589
31/12/2021	958	1572
31/1/2022	1539	2849
28/2/2022	2056	4428
31/3/2022	1344	2999
30/4/2022	982	1947
31/5/2022	988	1782
30/6/2022	992	1811
31/8/2022	894	3217
30/9/2022	1244	2582
31/10/2022	1344	2912
30/11/2022	1330	2500
31/12/2022	1330	2500
31/1/2023	1338	2517
28/2/2023	1288	2513
31/3/2023	1489	2842
30/4/2023	1255	2424
31/5/2023	2645	1399
Total	27095	48475

Figure 3: Example of WP Statistics for May 2023

ENVISION project website received 27095 visitors and 48475 page views in total. This number shows an apparent and essential increase in the generated web traffic, which has peaked concerning events, releases of newsletters, etc. The KPI for the project website visits is not just accomplished but exceeded.

2.2 Social Media

Communication means for the ENVISION project comprise a consistent presence in social networks. ENVISION LinkedIn, Twitter and Facebook were active from the beginning of the project; YouTube and SlideShare were opened later. The WP7 leader is responsible for keeping it updated, and every project partner is asked to send news and relevant information to the WP7 leader. An image accompanies posts as this delivers stronger engagement levels.

After the reviewers' recommendations after the 1st review meeting, we focus more on two social media channels: LinkedIn and Twitter.

Hashtags that are being used are the following:

[#earthobservation](#) [#agriculture](#) [#sustainable](#) [#environmental](#) [#monitoringsystem](#) [#payingagency](#) [#co designing](#) [#cocreation](#) [#farms](#) [#farming](#) [#agritech](#) [#innovation](#) [#certifications](#) [#certifyingbodis](#).

Table 3: Social Media Channels

Social Media Channel	Direct Link
LinkedIn	https://www.linkedin.com/company/envision-h2020/
Twitter	https://twitter.com/EnvisionH2020
Facebook	https://www.facebook.com/EnvisionH2020/
YouTube	https://www.youtube.com/channel/UC7a4V9GgwQhPAneqnmqmsxQ
SlideShare	https://www.slideshare.net/EnvisionH2020

Followers and posts are collected monthly for each social channel. The table shows that the number of followers is increasing every month.

Table 4: Followers/subscribers on the social channel

C3: Followers/subscribers on social networks					
Date	LinkedIn	Twitter	Facebook	SlideShare	YouTube
30/9/2020	79	28	35		
31/10/2020	114	43	55		
31/11/2020	128	44	58		
31/12/2020	133	46	59		
29/1/2021	190	49	65		
28/2/2021	217	66	68		
31/3/2021	238	76	73		
30/4/2021	249	87	80		/
31/5/2021	262	89	81		/
30/6/2021	277	102	82		/
31/7/2021	296	115	84		/
31/8/2021	300	118	86		/
30/9/2021	308	125	89		3
31/10/2021	322	130	94		6
30/11/2021	333	143	101		12
31/12/2021	354	144	104		15
31/1/2022	431	148	125	0	15
28/2/2022	454	158	126	0	20
31/3/2022	474	169	131	0	22
30/4/2022	476	173	132	1	23
31/5/2022	487	178	137	1	23
30/6/2022	489	186	136	1	23
31/8/2022	502	187	144	1	23
30/9/2022	507	194	144	1	23
31/10/2022	533	203	145	1	24

30/11/2022	565	230	148	2	25
31/12/2022	565	230	148	2	25
31/1/2023	568	233	149	2	25
28/2/2023	579	242	149	2	25
31/3/2023	581	245	149	2	25
30/4/2023	599	260	150	2	25
31/5/2023	600	265	150	2	24

Table 5: Number of posts on social channels

C3: Posts on social networks				
Year	Month	LinkedIn	Twitter	Facebook
2020	September	16	8	3
	October	22	0	3
	November	6	0	0
	December	8	1	0
2021	January	18	2	1
	February	15	7	4
	March	19	5	6
	April	19	10	5
	May	19	9	6
	June	10	11	5
	July	12	3	2
	August	8	1	2
	September	9	9	4
	October	8	5	2
	November	15	4	5
	December	7	5	4
2022	January	14	10	5
	February	6	9	4
	March	10	14	4
	April	4	3	1
	May	13	8	1
	June	4	4	1
	July	4	5	4
	August	1	4	1
	September	6	5	0
	October	16	29	13
	November	7	12	8
	December	7	12	8
2023	January	3	4	1
	February	10	11	6
	March	6	6	2
	April	2	1	1

	May	9	6	1
	Total:	333	223	113

The total number of followers and subscribers on social media is 1042 followers. An entire repetitive campaign is running through the project’s social media to increase their number to reach more followers and subscribers.

2.2.1 ENVISION LinkedIn page

The first social media channel of the ENVISION project is the LinkedIn page which allows ENVISION to communicate through the most popular professional networking platform. LinkedIn is a very effective tool for the project's exploitation strategy that can promote ENVISION as a disruptive idea on the market, triggering potentially interested Paying Agencies and Certification Bodies.

At the end of May, the ENVISION LinkedIn account has 600 followers. 333 posts were published.

Figure 4: LinkedIn followers analytics

Figure 5: LinkedIn Visitor highlights

Figure 6: LinkedIn Impressions

2.2.2 ENVISION Twitter page

The second social media channel is the ENVISION Twitter page. Until the end of May, the ENVISION Twitter account had 265 followers, and it is mainly used for the establishment of collaboration with EU initiatives related to the Earth Observation-based sector. ENVISION Twitter account following 194 accounts – similar projects, initiatives and organizations. There have been 223 tweets posted.

Figure 7: ENVISION Twitter account analytics

2.2.3 ENVISION Facebook page

Facebook effectively builds relationships and shows the human side of the ENVISION project, i.e. the partners, the events and presentations being attended, and the marketing materials produced. The content is more relaxed than on Twitter and LinkedIn, and overly scientific language is avoided. The ENVISION Facebook achieved 150 followers and published 113 posts from the beginning of the project.

Figure 8: ENVISION Facebook account analytics

2.2.4 ENVISION YouTube channel

Up to now, the ENVISION YouTube channel has 24 subscribers and 11 videos, including videos from webinars and presentations. Youtube analytics provide valuable information on views and engagementsT

Figure 9: ENVISION YouTube channel

Figure 10: ENVISION YouTube analytics

As seen from the image below, most views on the YouTube channel have the first video testimonial by LoginEKO.

Vsebina	Ogledi ↓	Čas gledanja (ure)	Naročniki	Prikazi	Razmerje med prikazi sličic in kliki
<input type="checkbox"/> Skupaj	243	5,2	1	1.067	6,3 %
<input type="checkbox"/> ENVISION Testimonial by LoginEKO	124 51,0 %	1,5 29,8 %	1 100 %	119	16,0 %
<input type="checkbox"/> ENVISION services assisting CAP requirements, develo...	36 14,8 %	2,0 37,8 %	0 0 %	230	3,9 %
<input type="checkbox"/> ENVISION services in practice - The case of Cyprus an...	18 7,4 %	0,5 9,4 %	0 0 %	214	3,3 %
<input type="checkbox"/> Earth Observation services in support of agriculture an...	16 6,6 %	0,5 8,7 %	0 0 %	214	4,2 %
<input type="checkbox"/> 18th edition of BioFest, with support of ENVISION proj...	14 5,8 %	0,2 3,4 %	0 0 %	0	—
<input type="checkbox"/> ENVISION – Coproducing Earth Observation based mo...	11 4,5 %	0,1 2,6 %	0 0 %	73	6,8 %
<input type="checkbox"/> ENVISION introduction video	7 2,9 %	0,1 2,0 %	1 100 %	43	14,0 %
<input type="checkbox"/> Deep Learning for Event Detection on Grasslands	7 2,9 %	0,2 4,0 %	0 0 %	82	6,1 %
<input type="checkbox"/> URDG Team ENVISION WP2	5 2,1 %	0,1 1,0 %	0 0 %	32	9,4 %
<input type="checkbox"/> BEYOND Centre of the National Observatory of Athens ...	2 0,8 %	0,0 0,4 %	0 0 %	25	8,0 %
<input type="checkbox"/> ENVISION project partner NOA_work	2 0,8 %	0,0 0,7 %	0 0 %	23	4,4 %
<input type="checkbox"/> RECAP the platform	1 0,4 %	0,0 0,3 %	0 0 %	12	8,3 %

Figure 11: ENVISION views of videos on YouTube

2.2.5 ENVISION SlideShare

The last channel in the social media channels that were open was ENVISION SlideShare. This channel is used to share presentation slides. With 17 SlideShares we achieved a total of 255 views in one year and all together until the end of May 773 views.

Figure 12: ENVISION SlideShare analytics

2.3 ENVISION e-Newsletters

Newsletters represent an efficient communication channel which provides a platform for sharing news on the project’s progress among project partners and external stakeholders. The newsletters are created and mailed through MailChimp. They are distributed to a mailing list containing subscriber information gathered through a signup form on the website. e-Newsletters are uploaded on the project website, distributed to a list of recipients and published in the social media channels.

Until now, four editions have been published, providing the news, the main outcomes, the project results.

Figure 13: ENVISION Newsletter page

Two newsletters were published in this reporting period:

- [The third edition of the ENVISION Newsletter](#) was published in April 2022. This edition presented the adaptations and modifications that have been performed in the ENVISION platform, members of the ENVISION Advisory Board and news from ENVISION business cases. It also included reportage from two ENVISION events: A clustering event titled "Earth Observation services in support of agriculture and Common Agricultural Policy" and the second one, "Coproducting Earth Observation based monitoring tools for sustainable agriculture".
- [The fourth edition of the ENVISION Newsletter](#) was published in December 2022. This edition presented the progress in work for ENVISION platform, with the announcement about the mobile application. We welcomed a new member of the Advisory Board and presented ENVISION's first results. The newsletter included information about ENVISION events, project meeting and publications.

Figure 14: ENVISION Newsletter #3

Figure 15: ENVISION Newsletter #3 analytics

Figure 16: ENVISION Newsletter #4

Most recent campaign performance

[See all campaigns](#)

Completed Campaign • Dec 28

ENVISION Newsletter #4

81 Recipients

Open Rate	56.8%	Total Clicks	14
Clicks Per Unique Open	6.5%	Orders	0
Successful Deliveries	80	Average Order Revenue	\$0.00
Total Opens	179	Total Revenue	\$0.00

Figure 17: ENVISION Newsletter #4 analytics

2.4 EuroGEOSS showcase

EuroGEOSS is a regional initiative launched in October 2017 by the European countries, the European Commission and organizations participating to the Group on Earth Observations (GEO). From 2018 onwards, the EuroGEOSS initiative plans to launch periodic Requests for Expressions of Intent. NOA submitted the Expression of Intent in year 2022.

Partners DRAXIS, AGROAPPS, NOA, ETAM, OCS and ITC attended the EuroGEOSS workshop held from the 7th to the 9th December 2022 in Athens:

Wednesday 7 December 2022, 11:15 - 13:00 (LT) | Parallel Sessions

ENVISION - The ENVISION Data Cube for Big Satellite Image Time- Series to support AI based national-scale agriculture Monitoring [15 min], Thanassis Drivas (NOA)

Thursday 8 December 2022, 09:00 - 10:30 (LT) | Parallel Sessions

Boosting the commercialisation aspects of R&D results | Room: Motivo

- ENVISION [5 min], Vasilis Spitadakis (ETAM)

Thursday 8 December 2022, 11:15 - 12:45 (LT) | Parallel Sessions

EuroGEO for agriculture in support of the partnership "Agriculture of Data" and the European Green Deal | Room: Electra

- ENVISION [7 min], Anastasios Karakostas (Draxis) & Ifigenia Tsioutsia (AgroApps)

Thursday 8 December 2022

Improving users' involvement in different stages of EO solutions development | Room: Motivo

- ENVISION, Svetlana Vitomirovic (Organic Control System)

Partners of the project have attended workshops/sessions where they have been able to present different angles of the ENVISION project. NOA has been presenting the technical aspect of the ENVISION data cube, while DRAXIS and AGROAPPS presented the general picture of the ENVISION project and its main goals. On the other hand, ETAM and OCS have been attending the session, where the commercialisation aspect and user involvement have been discussed. ETAM presented the commercialisation path of the ENVISION project, while OCS presented how users are involved in testing the ENVISION services.

2.5 Meetings with developers, open-source communities

All together ten meetings with developers and open-source communities were planned. In this period, five of these meetings have been done, and they are provided in the table below with all the details.

Table 6: Meetings with developers, open-source communities

Project Partner	Date	Developers	Meeting description
AgroApps	14/4/2022	CarbonEye Global	CarbonEye Global is Toronto-based startup in “hidden mode” that aims to utilize some EO-data for its AI-models. They approached us as they are interested in exploring how they can build on top of our services. They want to follow up on our project and see some results in order to incorporate them into their workflows (delivering services for emissions) under the scope of sustainability.
NOA	16/11/2022		Mowing detection intercompasion exercise (MODCiX) 1

Project Partner	Date	Developers	Meeting description
			This initiative aims to evaluate various mowing detection algorithms using openly accessible satellite data across Europe under a common validation system.
NOA	9/2/2023		Mowing detection intercomparison exercise (MODCiX) 2 This initiative aims to evaluate various mowing detection algorithms using openly accessible satellite data across Europe under a common validation system.
NOA	3/4/2023	CaALLISTO project	Liaison with CALLISTO developers A liaison meeting between ENVISION and Callisto developers presenting their own services and infrastructures
NOA	12/4/2023		Mowing detection intercomparison exercise (MODCiX) 3 This initiative aims to evaluate various mowing detection algorithms using openly accessible satellite data across Europe under a common validation system.

2.6 Informal person-to-person meetings with stakeholders

On-site visits to targeted potential customers and meetings with stakeholders at the national and EU level were planned. These meetings are held beyond the project events aiming at presenting ENVISION's results and activities at different stages of the project development.

Table 7: Informal person-to-person meetings with stakeholders

Project Partner	Date	Organisation	Meeting description
AgroApps	16/05/2022	Wageningen	A meeting was conducted with Mireille Vanhiltten from Wageningen to discuss the ENVISION project and specifically for the organic service. She has great expertise and

Project Partner	Date	Organisation	Meeting description
			is interested in this specific field and she introduced us to a national organic project.
OCS	29/08/2022	Ministry of Agriculture of the Republic of Srpska	The aim of the visit of representatives of the Ministry of Agriculture of the Republic of Srpska (Bosnia and Herzegovina) was to improve existing and acquire new knowledge, skills, and competencies in the sector of organic production. At the same time, OCS presented ENVISION project in the part of the discussion about digital technologies in agriculture. OCS presented what is ENVISION and what will be benefits in the future from a project like this.
OCS	09/09/2022	USAID	Meeting with partners from North Macedonia - Cooperation between Serbia and North Macedonia regarding the development of digitalization in agriculture and innovative projects. General manager of OCS presented to representative of USAID in North Macedonia what is ENVISION and what will be benefits in the future from a project like this.
OCS	23/09/2022	President of the association of organic producers	The 2nd Organic Fest of Srpska was opened on the premises of TC Delta, organized by the Chamber of the Republic of Srpska and the Ministry of Agriculture, Forestry and Water Management of the Republic of Srpska. The event gathered around 20 certified producers of organic products from the Republic of Srpska, the Federation of Bosnia and Herzegovina, Croatia and Serbia, and it was officially opened by the Minister of Agriculture Ph.D. Boris Pašalić. Organic products were exhibited for two days in TC Delta Banja Luka, and the thematic part continued on the Chamber's premises, where a round table was held on the topic "Organic production as a development opportunity for the Western Balkans, yes or no?" The General manager of Organic Control System presented ENVISION project to an organic farmer and the President of the association of organic producers.

Project Partner	Date	Organisation	Meeting description
OCS	23/09/2022	Ministry of Agriculture	The General manager of Organic Control System presented ENVISION project to the Minister of Agriculture PhD. Boris Pašalić.
OCS	23/09/2022	Paying agency of Republic Srpska	General manager of the Organic Control System presented ENVISION project to the Head of Paying agency of Republic of Srpska Ljubinko Kecman and his assistant Nataša Božić Zavišić.
OCS	23/09/2022	Chamber of commerce and industry of Serbia	The General manager of the Organic Control System presented ENVISION project to representative of Chamber of commerce and industry of Serbia, Veljko Jovanović.
OCS	24/09/2022	Agriculture expert service	The 2nd Organic Fest of Srpska was opened on the premises of TC Delta, organized by the Chamber of the Republic of Srpska and the Ministry of Agriculture, Forestry and Water Management of the Republic of Srpska. Inspectors of Organic Control System presented ENVISION project to senior expert associate in the agricultural expert service, Milovan Ćučić.

Project Partner	Date	Organisation	Meeting description
OCS	24/09/2022	Chamber of commerce and industry of Republic of Srpska	Inspector of Organic Control System presented ENVISION project to representative of Chamber of commerce and industry of Republic of Srpska, Head of sector of Agriculture, water, fisheries, food and tobacco industry, Dragan Šepa.
OCS	24/09/2022	Prijedor cluster	Inspector of Organic Control System presented ENVISION project to senior expert associate in the agricultural expert service from Prijedor cluster, Radenko Topalović.
OCS	24/09/2022	Organic Farmer	Inspector of Organic Control System presented ENVISION project to organic farmer, Mile Bajalica.
Inosens	17/10/2022	FruitCREWS	This Action aims at understanding the physiological behaviour of fruit tree crops in response to drought stress, in different environments, and identifying the best tools to monitor plant water status in real time while allowing growers to precisely schedule irrigation through the adoption of new technologies. Activities will focus on 1) identifying the most useful physiological parameters to quantify drought stress using cost-effective and user-friendly sensor tools; 2) comparing and assessing the performance of existing models to quantify

Project Partner	Date	Organisation	Meeting description
			<p>plant water needs under drought, for possible implementation in decision support systems (DSSs); 3) defining the most effective (deficit) irrigation strategies for different crops and environments and 4) identifying gaps for improving existing DSSs based on the knowledge generated by the network, while taking actions to facilitate their diffusion among stakeholders and adoption by end-users. Results from this Action will provide relevant information for making a step forward towards a more sustainable irrigation management of European orchards. In cooperation with researchers, SMEs, service providers, local water authorities and fruit producers, knowledge resulting from this network activity will be disseminated to a wide spectrum of European stakeholders and to the general public, making European fruit production more resilient and raising awareness of the problems related to water scarcity.</p>
NOA	23/11/2022	FPCUP	<p>The main goal of this webinar was to introduce the Copernicus services, the Sentinel missions and the access to data through the Hellenic Mirror Site and the Sentinel Missions-Federated Access and also other web services.</p>
NOA	30/11/2022	HellaGIS: Big data and Machine Learning for crop classification	<p>An interactive presentation on the application of Machine Learning on Big Earth Observation Data - in which a methodology for crop classification using machine learning models and satellite data (Sentinel-2) was presented in a jupyter notebook environment, in an area of Cyprus. More specifically, the structure of the worksho was as follows: - Explanatory analysis of the data - Data pre-processing - Classification of crops using machine learning - Visualization and understanding</p>

Project Partner	Date	Organisation	Meeting description
			of the results Basic knowledge of Python was necessary to attend the workshop.
URDG	26/01/2023	Space-tech Meets Agri-Tech	<p>The European Space Agency, the UK Space Agency and others have recognised the potential for spacetech as a driver for collaboration, innovation and enterprise, and we will also be hearing about those with an opportunity to learn more about how to access funding for companies, and wider geographies.</p> <p>New Anglia LEP has led the development of the Space Sector Plan for Norfolk and Suffolk which has formally put this region on the map of space clusters recognised by the UK Space Agency, Satellite Applications Catapult and European Space Agency. The plan sets out the widespread downstream application of space technologies in the agri-food sector and seeks to support new opportunities by attracting new space-related funding into this region.</p> <p>Met with Agtelligence, Satellite Applications Catapult who were key ENVISION lighthouse customers.</p>
NOA	10/02/2023	ENVISION CAPO Online meeting	A meeting to inform stakeholders of Cyprus about ENVISION services updates.
<p>The screenshot shows a presentation slide titled "ENVISION CAPO ONLINE MEETING" with the subtitle "WP3 – CCTM Product Updated". It includes the logo of the National Observatory of Athens and the date "10/02/2023". At the bottom, there is a small text box stating: "This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 869366. Legal notice: The intellectual property and its content remain only the author's own, therefore the CAPO is not responsible for any use that may be made of the information it contains." Logos for the European Union and BEYOND are also visible.</p>			
INOS	27/04/2023	DRG4Food workshop on digital responsibility goals	The DRG4Food project recently conducted a workshop that focused on embedding Digital Responsibility Goals into the food sector. The purpose of the workshop was to promote responsible digital practices within the food industry, and to discuss ways in which technology can be leveraged to

Project Partner	Date	Organisation	Meeting description
			<p>achieve this goal. The workshop provided an opportunity for experts in the field to share their insights and experiences, and to collaborate on strategies for promoting digital responsibility in the food sector.</p> <p>During the discussion, ENVISION was presented as an exemplary case of how information and communication technology (ICT) solutions can enhance privacy, promote fair data practices, ensure trustworthy algorithms, and increase transparency in the food production process. It was acknowledged that the two projects could further benefit from opening up to the developer community, particularly through participating in DRG4FOOD open calls. These calls provide opportunities for collaboration, knowledge sharing, and access to resources that could help improve the projects' outcomes and impact.</p>
INOS	4/05/2023	Meeting with representatives of University of Donja Gorica	<p>InoSens team represented by Maja Žikić (Standardisation Lead, T6.5) and Vladimir Mrkajić met with Dr Sandra Tinaj from University of Donja Gorica (Podgovrica, Montenegro). We presented the Envision project and its main achievement. We also discussed the technology behind the Envision platform.</p>
INOS	22/05/2023	Meetings In Agri Fair in Novi Sad	<p>A part of our team at InoSens visited the Agri Fair in Novi Sad. We were excited to meet AgTech providers, farmers, standardisation/ certification and insurance providers and discuss sustainable innovation in the agrifood sector. We also shared insights from our ENVISION H2020 project.</p>

Project Partner	Date	Organisation	Meeting description
			Representatives from OTP Bank were engaged in a meeting where we discussed the significance of integrating a platform like ENVISION into their operations. Additionally, we had a meeting with a standardization body from Hungary and an insurance provider called Globos. To further explore the integration of the platform into their respective businesses, follow-up meetings were arranged.

2.7 Project events (seminars/workshops)

According to the project plan every partner shall organise an event/seminar/workshop and actively participate in events organised by other partners. Guidelines for managing the ENVISION events were prepared.

Project Partner	Date	Name of the event	Description
URDG	17/3/2022	Agri-Food Economics and Marketing Weekly Seminars	<p>This is an internal seminar organised by the department of Agri-Food Economics and Marketing School of Agriculture, Policy and Development. This is a weekly event where a number of different topics are presented in respect to the main themes and research interests of the department. The attendees as well as the presenters are from the internal and external network of the University of Reading.</p> <p>Agenda: Seminar title: ENVISION – Coproducing Earth Observation based monitoring tools for sustainable agriculture</p> <p>ENVISION is an EU Horizon 2020 project that aims to address the need for continuous, automated, large scale, and uninterrupted monitoring of farm management activities with respect to sustainability. In this way, it aims to reinforce monitoring of cross-compliance measures through the identification of</p>

Project Partner	Date	Name of the event	Description
			<p>practices that lead to environmental degradation. To do this, ENVISION involves a big network of potential customers including Paying Agencies, Certification Bodies, and farmers, as well as researchers and agri-food technology developers across Europe, in a coproduction framework facilitated by the University of Reading. In this talk, we will present an overview of ENVISION's products and services and discuss the main challenges we have identified thus far in coordinating an effective and efficient coproduction framework that involves such an interdisciplinary and multicultural group of stakeholders.</p>
NOA	11/7/2022	BEYOND Dialogues	<p>Presentations in the BEYOND Center of Excellence</p>
OCS	12/10/2022	ENVISION EVENT – Digitalization to increase economic, environmental and social sustainability of agriculture - introduction of new agro-technological solutions	<p>A panel discussion on the topic of digitalization of agriculture was held as part of the 18th BIOFEST, on Wednesday, October 12, 2022, from 12:00 p.m. to 2:00 p.m. at the Open University in Subotica and at the same time via the Zoom application. The language of the discussion was Serbian and English with simultaneous translation.</p>
			<p>The panel's moderator and introducer was Mr. Milan Šolaja, director of the Vojvodina ICTV Cluster, who gave further guidelines to the panelists and all other participants through his introductory speech on digitization in agriculture. Panel broke into two parts: first was about historical development of the field and current state of the affairs, and after that panellists looked to the future.</p> <p>Introduction of participants.</p> <p>Part I, current state of the affairs</p> <p>1. Mr. Raketić: Law on Organic production and digitalization of organic agriculture</p>

Project Partner	Date	Name of the event	Description
	<p>2. Dr Emanuel Lekakis: presentation - The distinction of organic vs conventional farming practices</p> <p>3. Dr Mrkajić: question – your view on how much Serbia has utilized EU funds in advancing agriculture digitalization</p> <p>4. Mr. Pejak: presentation – Application of IS in agriculture</p> <p>Part II, future</p> <p>1. Mr. Pejak: presentation – Future of Agriculture</p> <p>2. Mr. Raketić: question – policy makers’ view on implementation of strategic documents in agriculture, especially Smart Specialization Strategy of Serbia (4S)</p> <p>3. Ms. Tsioutsia: presentation – The ENVISION solutions</p> <p>4. Ms. Vitomirović: presentation – Challenges in organic agriculture digitalization</p> <p>Q&A</p> <p>Wrapping up</p> <p>The event was very successful and well-covered by the media.</p>		
NOA	25/10/2022	ENVISION services assisting CAP requirements, developed by the National Observatory of Athens	This webinar aimed to reach audiences such as Paying Agencies, Research Institutes, Farmer associations and Industry to showcase services that have been developed by NOA in the framework for
	<p>ENVISION, such as Grassland mowing events detection, Analytics on Vegetation & Soil Index timeseries and DataCube End Point service, as well as Cultivated Crop Type Maps.</p> <p>AGENDA</p> <p>11:00 – 11:05 Welcome note</p> <p>11:05 – 11:20 Grassland mowing events detection , (National Observatory of Athens – Jason Tsardanidis)</p> <p>11:20 – 11:40 Analytics on Vegetation & Soil Index time-series and DataCube End Point service, (National Observatory of Athens – Thanassis Drivas)</p>		

Project Partner	Date	Name of the event	Description
			11:40-11:55 Cultivated Crop Type Maps, (National Observatory of Athens – Jason Tsardanidis) 11:55 – 12:00 Q&A session
AgroApps	22/2/2023	Open source solutions and commercialisation	Christos Bacharakis, as the Code Contributor Program Manager of GitLab community, presented the added value of the open-solutions and how they can empower a company’s portfolio under the right license. AGENDA 12:30 -12:40 Welcome note 12:40 – 13:30 Open-source solutions <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • What is open-source software? • How to choose the right license? • How you can benefit from an open-source solution. • What are the main drawbacks, and what should you take into consideration when designing an open-source solution? 13:30 – 14:00 Q&A session
CAPO	28/2/2023	ENVISION services in practice – The case of Cyprus	This webinar aimed to reach audiences such as Paying Agencies, Research Institutes, Farmer associations and Industry to present the services developed by ENVISION and its application in Cyprus Agricultural Payment Organization (CAPO). It also showcased services that have been developed by the National Observatory of Athens (NOA). AGENDA 12:00 – 12:05 Welcome note 12:05 – 12:20 The Cypriot Business Case Cyprus Agricultural Payments Organisation – George Farkonis 12:20-12:45 An automated end-to-end framework for CAP monitoring. Lessons learned from the Cypriot use case. National Observatory of Athens – Jason Tsardanidis, Thanassis Drivas 12:45 – 13:00 Q&A session
UDRG	29/3/2023	How can Earth Observation technologies advance	This interactive workshop explored how Earth Observation can advance Sustainable Agricultural Development,

Project Partner	Date	Name of the event	Description
		<p>Sustainable Agricultural Development?</p>	<p>and the industry drivers for these technologies.</p> <p>We heard from keynote speakers on the why, how and what of the role of earth observation technologies in achieving sustainability and net zero targets in agriculture. We hosted a couple of discussion sessions in the afternoon, along with interactive poster and exhibition time over lunch.</p> <p>Our speakers discussed the practical industry drivers for sustainable agricultural development, and how earth observation tools can be used to monitor sustainability indicators, incentivise change, and inform on-farm decisions. It was also showcased a case study example of the co-development of continuous, large scale earth observation monitoring tools like ENVISION.</p> <p>More about the event can be found here: https://envision-h2020.eu/wp-content/uploads/2023/06/Earth-Observation-event-29-March-Agri-TechE-Reading-University-Event-report.pdf</p> <p>https://envision-h2020.eu/wp-content/uploads/2023/06/Earth-Observation-event-29-March-Agri-TechE-Reading-University-Poster-abstracts-live-stream-link.pdf</p>
<p>NPA</p>	<p>29/3/2023</p>	<p>Agricultural exhibition "Ką pasėsi..."</p>	<p>Agricultural exhibition "Ką pasėsi..." is being held annually since 1996. It is the largest exhibition for agro-industry innovations in the Baltic States. Around 300 companies, organisations and about 300 small traders from Lithuania and abroad participated in the exhibition in 2023. Over three days, around 70,000 visitors came to the exhibition. The visitors of the exhibition included farmers, representatives of farmer associations, agricultural consultants, representatives of SME's, scientists, policy makers, general public.</p>

Project Partner	Date	Name of the event	Description
			<p>NPA took part in the national exhibition "Ką pasėsi...2023" where in parallel to the introduction about the NPA activities, Horizon 2020 ENVISION project results, including the developed platform, algorithms and the mobile application, were presented.</p> <p>During the 3 days of the exhibition, around 2000 people visited the NPA stand. In the course of three days, during the exhibition daily operating hours, i.e., from 9:00 am to 17:00, four times a day: at 10:00; 11:00; 13:00 and 14:00 hrs workshops / live demo sessions took place at the NPA stand. The visitors of the stand (groups of approx. 30 people per one session) familiarized themselves with the Horizon 2020 ENVISION project results: project platform, algorithms and mobile app as well as with the practical application of these tools. During the intervals between the sessions, the exhibition visitors had a unique opportunity to familiarize themselves with the satellite recognition results after having found in the map their concrete area and concrete field. Those who wanted, had an opportunity to try the remote virtuality (RV) eyeglasses and to have a look at their declared fields from space, as well as to watch the process of getting the satellite recognition results – compliance interpretation. Most frequent visitors at the NPA stand were farmers, not to mention scientists and policy makers, who were very interested in the ENVISION tools, comprising 4 algorithms for: meadow's mowing event detection, minimal soil coverage, crop harvesting event detection and crop type map, with the algorithms accuracy ranging from 94% to 100%.</p>
AgroApps	12/102023	ENVISION_ Webinar for Lighthouse Customers Group	At the webinar, we discussed more the project and presented to our Lighthouse customers the progress we have made

Project Partner	Date	Name of the event	Description
			<p>with our services up to now, the platform that we have developed and discussed how we can collaborate</p>

2.8 Policy session – Panta Rhei Conferences

ENVISION project team participated in two Panta Rhei Conferences. In Bucharest, we presented the results and outcomes of our previous work to the paying agencies in the sector of the EAGGF (European Agriculture Guidance and Guarantee Funds) and EAFRD (European Agricultural Funds for Rural Development) within the European Union and their coordinating bodies.

ENVISION services are tailor-made to help Paying Agencies at the technical implementation of the measures taken in application of the Common Agricultural Policy (CAP).

2.8.1 58th Panta Rhei Conference Bucharest

Panta Rhei secretariat and the Romanian Agency for Payment and Intervention in Agriculture hosted the 58th Panta Rhei conference in Bucharest, Romania, from 19th to 21st of October, 2022.

The ENVISION project team attended the 58th Panta Rhei conference in Bucharest, Romania. We were honoured and privileged to be there to present the results of our previous work. Discussions have been taking place, where team members presented the benefits ENVISION services offer to the paying agencies supporting CAP measures.

Figure 18: ENVISION project team at the 58th Panta Rhei Conference

The Second day of the Panta Rhei conference was in full swing. After visiting the dairy farm one day before and learning about the Romanian agriculture sector, this day's session was about IT tools that support CAP measures and different experiences from members.

Figure 19: ENVISION team attracting participants

2.8.2 59th Panta Rhei Conference Slovenia

The Secretariat of Panta Rhei organized the LIX Panta Rhei Conference scheduled from 24th to 26th May 2023, in Ljubljana, Slovenia. During this conference, the prevalent subjects have been Preparation for the development of the information systems for supporting new CAP, including monitoring systems and possible technical solutions for information systems, data management, and new tools for obligatory and other reporting systems.

During this Panta Rhei Conference a workshop was co-organised (ENVISION, SPACE4GREEN and MEF4CAP).

The aim of the workshop was to present and discuss the solutions derived by the ENVISION, SPACE4GREEN and MEF4CAP projects, that can support the current and future needs of the CAP monitoring in the frame of an automated decision-making system.

More specifically, ENVISION presented the results of a number of business cases; Lithuanian, Cypriot and Flemish Paying Agencies regarding the services and the tools that they have used during the 2-years pilot implementation phase.

On the other hand, the SPACE4GREEN presented how new technologies such as Copernicus data, GNSS and blockchain could contribute to the automation of CAP and environmental sustainability monitoring process.

Furthermore, the MEF4CAP project presented some of the most important emerging ICT technologies for the agricultural domain and how the use of such technologies could contribute to future monitoring and evaluation process.

Through this workshop, it was expected to draw out lessons learned both from the projects and the relevant stakeholders' feedback and synthesize a roadmap for further developments and solutions for the future monitoring and evaluation system

The presentations at the workshop followed in this order:

- **Ifigenia-Matia Tsiotsia (AgroApps)**
 - Complete System Rethink
 - AgroApps: Mobile Apps for Modern Agriculture

- **George Groutas, George Farkonis (CAPO)**
 - The Cypriot Business Case

- **Tuna Coppens (EV ILVO)**
 - ENVISION: WP3 Earth Observation data products: Organic carbon monitoring

- **Bas Philip (LV)**

- Flemish BC soil organic carbon
- AgroApp: Mobile Apps for Modern Agriculture – Flemish vision of FaST

- **Jason Tsardanidis (NOA)**

- ENVISION – Earth Observation Data Products

- **Aušrius Kučinskas (NPA)**

- ENVISION, BC1: Monitoring multiple environmental and climate requirements of CAP – Lithuania
- AgroApp: Mobile Apps for Modern Agriculture – NPA Agro

Prior to the workshop, a questionnaire was prepared and shared with all the members of the Panta Rhei Conference. The workshop attracted more than 50 participants and fruitful discussion has been conducted. The outcomes of the questionnaire as well as the workshop have been presented at the end of the conference by CAPO.

The first part of the presentation consisted of an analysis of a Questionnaire sent to the Member States before the start of the conference.

The second part was a summary of a short brainstorming session that took place during the workshop, where the participants gave their answers on issues regarding monitoring services and the new CAP.

Figure 20: Presentation of the results of Workshop 2 at the Panta Rhei Conference

2.9 External events

Events are indispensable for distributing information about the project as a place to initiate cooperation and collaboration activities. The project partners attend external events (industry fairs, conferences and meetings) to present ENVISION, its activities and results.

Table 8: External events attended by ENVISION projects partners

Project Partner	Date	Name of the event	Description
NPA	2/4/2022	Agricultural exhibition "Ką pasėsi..."	<p>Agricultural exhibition "Ką pasėsi..." is held since 1996. It is the largest exhibition for agro-industry innovations in the Baltic States. Usually, about 300 companies, organizations and about 300 small traders from Lithuania and abroad participate in "Ką pasėsi...". Over three days, the exhibition is visited by around 70,000 visitors. More info https://expoacademia.lt/lt-ka-pasesi-lankytojams-parodosprograma</p> <p>NPA participated in a national exhibition "Ką pasėsi...2022" and presented tools, mobile applications and other products, that are under development or have already been developed within the scope of Horizon 2020 projects, including NIVA, DIONE, ENVISION, etc. Tools were presented via live demo and each farmer could look at his area of interest and see how augmented reality works in action. NPA exhibition stand was popular among the policy makers too, who were mainly interested in new tools, that could be used in Area monitoring system as of 2023.</p>
EV ILVO	21/4/2022	MRV systems for carbon farming activities	We examined how Envision SOC services can support MRC systems in their monitoring activities.
ITC	21/5/2022	Ploutos Open days	The Open day was organised under the umbrella of Ploutos H2020 project, focusing on field demonstration of precision farming technologies, including the use of Earth Observation data. The meeting has been visited by farmers, agricultural advisors, students,

Project Partner	Date	Name of the event	Description
			<p>developers, industry and other interested parties.</p> <p>At the event, ITC presented activities and services of ENVISION project.</p> <p>Several discussions with farmers and advisory service representatives have been conducted during and after the event and demonstration activities. The use of Earth observation data and services is highly appreciated and the acceptance of more advanced farmers is relatively high (some of them are covered by the ENVISION project), especially with the Soil organic carbon monitoring which could be used for monitoring and verification of precision farming practices. One section of the event was dedicated to conservation farming and organic farming, with a discussion around how to use EO services to distinguish between organic and conventional farming. This service was of special interest for agricultural advisors.</p>
INOS	21/6/2023	Third Virtual EXCELSIOR Workshop on 'Entrepreneurship and Innovation in Earth Observation'	<p>On June 21st, 2022, the 'EXCELSIOR' H2020 Teaming Project Consortium and the ERATOSTHENES Centre of Excellence (ECoE) of the Cyprus University of Technology organize the Third Virtual EXCELSIOR Workshop on 'Entrepreneurship and Innovation in Earth Observation'. This Workshop was a part of a series of annual workshops with participation of all national and international stakeholders of EXCELSIOR, addressing all the different activities of the ECoE, i.e. infrastructure, research, education and innovation through entrepreneurship.</p>
ITC	23/8/2022	60th International fair of agriculture and food (AGRA)	<p>AGRA presents the latest production, breeding and processing technologies with leading global brands</p>
			<p>in agricultural and forestry machinery and food processing equipment. It offers top-quality crops, food products, dishes and wines. There are also programs on packaging, modern agricultural construction, tools and equipment, air</p>

Project Partner	Date	Name of the event	Description
		ki zavod, Murska Sobota	<p>conditioning techniques and the use of renewable energy sources.</p> <p>It is a six-day event featuring talks, forums and discussions from leading international agricultural policy experts about:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • International year of fisheries and aquaculture • European year of youth • Innovation and digitalization • Agriculture in the future • Climate change and water resource <p>Institute of Agriculture and Forestry Murska Sobota is one of ENVISION Lighthouse's customers that will test and validate ENVISION services. At the fair, ITC presented ENVISION project.</p>
INOS	12/10/2022	18. International organic food festival BIOFEST 2022	<p>"Digitalization to increase economic, environmental and social sustainability of agriculture - introduction of new agro-technological solutions."</p> <p>Invited participants on panel are – certification bodies, paying agencies, IT sector, farmers, representatives of agriculture ministries, representatives of chambers, partners of Envision project, institutions and others.</p> <p>The ENVISION project was presented to a variety of local (Serbian) stakeholders. National TV covered the event, and representative of InoSens, Vladimir Mrkajic, had a chance to explain the overall idea of the ENVISION project to wide audience.</p>
EV ILVO	17/11/2022	Workshop : Are future farmers flying farmers?	<p>Use of robots, drones, and satellites in agriculture:</p> <p>Today's agriculture has transformed into a high-tech enterprise that most 20th-century farmers might barely recognize. Self-driving machinery and flying robots able to automatically survey and treat crops will become common place on farms that practice what's come to be called precision agriculture. The ultimate purpose of all this high-tech gadgetry is optimization, from both an economic and an environmental standpoint. This thematic worksho pointed out and</p>

Project Partner	Date	Name of the event	Description
			<p>showcase different solutions that are on the market, ready to be used by farmers worldwide.</p> <p>The presentation "Satellite data in Agriculture" was made by Panagiotis Ilias.</p>
NOA	1/12/2022	12th Panhellenic Conference of HellasGIs	<p>As part of the workshops of the 12th Panhellenic Conference of HellasGIs, NOA has presented at the workshop "Big data and Machine Learning for crop classification", by Mr. Jason Tsardanidis and Alkibiadis Koukos of the BEYOND Center of Excellence of the National Observatory of Athens, in which a methodology for crop classification using machine learning models and satellite data (Sentinel-2) was presented in a jupyter notebook environment, in an area of Cyprus. More specifically, the structure of the workshop is as follows:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Explanatory analysis of the data - Data pre-processing - Crop classification using machine learning - Visualization and understanding of the results
AgroApps	12/3/2023	AgroThessaly	<p>AgroThessaly (14th Pan-Hellenic fair for agriculture and livestock), is a regional exhibition that came out from the strategic collaboration of TIF-HELEXPO and the Municipality of Larissa.</p> <p>Aiming to promote the Greek products as well as the global agro-livestock production, Agrothessaly introduces all developments about the new technologies, creating in the most developed rural area of the country, an important networking point for domestic and international commercial contacts.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Presentation of the envision services to farmers/ agricultural consultants. <p>The main key takeaway is the willingness of this target group to get familiar with new technologies that could assist them to follow up with the new regulations and be compliant with the rules posed by the new cap, especially in the frame of environmental measures.</p>

Project Partner	Date	Name of the event	Description

2.10 Presentations/attending at International Conferences

The partners attended the following International Conferences:

Table 9: Presentations/attending at International Conferences

Project Partner	Date	Name of the conference	Description
UDRG	22/03/2022	Agri-Tech and ELMs – the Innovation Enablers	<p>We explore how technology can help agriculture deliver environmental benefits alongside sustainable food production and the achievement of industry net zero targets.</p> <p>The UK's new "Environment and Land Management" (ELM) scheme will see a shift towards incentivising farmers to deliver "public goods" in exchange for public money. The National Farmers' Union also has an ambitious plan to reach net zero by 2040. It is still unclear how to measure, monitor and manage many of the elements of these "public goods" – a major risk for farmers as they transition into the new system. This event aimed to provide an opportunity to hear from farmers and advisors that have participated in early trials and also from the technologists and researchers that are developing techniques and tools to assist them.</p>
ITC	11/5/2022	FMIS and their interaction with CAP PAs (DEMETER – NIVA online workshop)	<p>The objective of the workshop was to present the DEMETER and NIVA projects, pilots and datasharing principles and discuss potential areas of collaboration. ITC is a partner (pilot coordinator) in DEMETER, while NIVA is a sister project of ENVISION, with collaboration possibilities discussed</p>

Project Partner	Date	Name of the conference	Description
			<p>already in the past, while ENVISION and NIVA organised a clustering event in February 2022.</p> <p>Both projects are essential for cross-project collaboration in EO monitoring for CAP and data-sharing, which are both the focus of ENVISION project.</p> <p>The agenda was following:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> 10:00 – 10:10 The DEMETER Project & the architecture (Kevin, Ioanna) 10:10 – 10:55 The DEMETER pilots (40-45 min) 10:55 – 11:05 The NIVA project & the architecture (Tragsa) 11:05 – 11:50 The NIVA use cases 11:50 – 12:05 Datasharing and data models (Dominique & Raul Palma) 12:05 – 12:20 Open discussion, Q&A,.. <p>ENVISION will continue to pursue collaboration with both projects in terms of:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - NIVA: sharing information about ENVISION business case scenarios, ENVISION services and NIVA use cases. ENVISION and NIVA will furthermore exploit possibility to organise the next mutual event and continue discussions on testing ENVISION/NIVA services. - DEMETER: cross-fertilising on pilots covering data sharing and EO services. Intensifying collaboration between ENVISION and DEMETER is planned.
NOA	23/05/2022	Living Planet Symposium 2022	<p>Attracting thousands of scientists and data users, ESA's Living Planet Symposia are amongst the biggest Earth observation conferences in the world. For decades now Earth observation has played a fundamental role in advancing our understanding of how our planet works and how it is being affected by climate change. While the need to continue to advance our</p>

Project Partner	Date	Name of the conference	Description
<p>A3.01 Towards global rangeland monitoring using Sentinel-1/2/3</p> <p>Deep Learning Methods for Grassland Activity Monitoring</p> <p>Mon, 23 May, 2022</p> <p>Iason Tsandamis, Vasilios Sitokostantinou, Alkiviadis Koukos, Athanasios Drivas and Dr. Charalampos Kontoes</p>			<p>knowledge and monitor global change remains paramount, Earth observation has entered a new era where it is playing a key role in a myriad of everyday applications to improve daily lives and is also becoming increasingly relevant for the competitive business sector.</p>
NOA	25/05/2023	Living Planet Symposium 2022	<p>Attracting thousands of scientists and data users, ESA's Living Planet Symposia are amongst the biggest Earth observation conferences in the world. For decades now Earth observation has played a</p>
<p>A3.10.1 Novel in-situ collection for agricultural and forest structure applications</p> <p>DataCAP: Sentinel datacubes, crowdsourced street-level images and annotated benchmark datasets for the monitoring of the CAP</p> <p>Wed, 25 May, 2022</p> <p>Vasileios Sitokostantinou (vsito@noa.gr) Alkiviadis Koukos, George Choumos and Dr. Charalampos Kontoes</p>			<p>fundamental role in advancing our understanding of how our planet works and how it is being affected by climate change. While the need to continue to advance our knowledge and monitor global change remains paramount, Earth observation has entered a new era where it is playing a key role in a myriad of everyday applications to improve daily lives and is also becoming increasingly relevant for the competitive business sector.</p>
ILVO	08/06/2022	EIP-AGRI brokerage event 'Get involved in the EU Mission: A Soil Deal for Europe'	<p>This event offered matchmaking sessions through face-to-face meetings and networking amongst farmers, advisors, researchers, and other relevant stakeholders to support the preparation of proposals for the EU Mission 'A Soil Deal for Europe' call that was launched in May. Additionally, the activity created conditions for exchanging knowledge and innovative ideas and practices (living labs and lighthouses), that may inspire potential applicants to take part in the next EU Mission call. The main objective of the brokerage event is to support the Horizon Europe call for proposals under the</p>
<p>EIP-AGRI BROKERAGE EVENT 'GET INVOLVED IN THE EU MISSION: A SOIL DEAL FOR EUROPE' 8-9 JUNE 2022 - BRUSSELS, BELGIUM</p> <p>PROGRAMME – update 1 June 2022</p> <p>Day 1: Wednesday 8 June 2022</p>			

Project Partner	Date	Name of the conference	Description
	<p>Breakout Session I: 'Lighthouses and living labs: concrete experiences'</p> <p>Participants will be able to choose between 4 parallel breakout rooms. The parallel group discussions will be preceded by 1 inspirational example, followed by group discussions on the concept and implementation of living labs and lighthouses in the context of the EU Soil Mission.</p> <p>9:45 10:45</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Breakout room 1: Korinna Varga (Hungary) • Breakout room 2: Panos Ilias (Belgium) • Breakout room 3: Gianfranco Maltese (Italy) • Breakout room 4: Didier Stilman (Belgium) <p>10:45 11:15 Coffee break</p>		<p>EU Mission: A Soil Deal for Europe. Specific objectives include:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - improving awareness on the EU Soil Mission and its work programme 2022 and the opportunities offered under its calls, - supporting future applicants in finding potential partners, and - sharing further information on the call and its topics, thus contributing to improving the quality of the proposals. <p>We present how we used EV ILVO Living Lab practices to develop the SOC service.</p>
URDG	24/6/2022	Groundswell	<p>The Groundswell event is an outdoor event providing a forum for farmers and anyone interested in food production or the environment to learn about the theory and practical applications of Conservation Agriculture or regenerative systems. It is a two-day event featuring talks, forums and discussions from leading international soil health experts, experienced arable and livestock farmers, agricultural policy experts, direct-drill demonstrations and AgTech innovators.</p> <p>Contact with Agritech_E, the Soil Association and the Farm Carbon Toolkit.</p>
NOA	27/6/2022	2022 IEEE 14th Image, Video, and Multidimensional Signal Processing Workshop (IVMSP 2022)	
			<p>IVMSP 2022 was the 14th of the biennial events that are organised by the Image, Video, and Multidimensional Signal Processing Technical Committee (IVMSP TC) of the IEEE Signal Processing Society with the aim to promote and guide the advancement of the field of image, video, and multidimensional signal processing. This includes those areas listed under all EDICS categories of the IEEE Transactions on Image Processing and the IEEE</p>

Project Partner	Date	Name of the conference	Description
			<p>Transactions on Computational Imaging, as well as under the EDICS subcategory Multidimensional Signal Processing of IEEE Transactions on Signal Processing.</p>
EV ILVO	11/7/2022	CAPIGI 2022	<p>CAPIGI-22 was focused on the latest developments in data science and data platforms, and to successful data performance in agriculture. Content was agriculture and digital business where satellites, drones, IoT, robotics, GNSS and sensors deliver geo-spatial data that has become a core asset to farmers, advisors, suppliers, governments, and others in the agrifood domain. Data offers opportunities to monitor and benchmark farm performance on productivity, resource use efficiency, environmental and climate performance and other themes.</p>
INOS	21/09/2022	"Skilling up the Western Balkan agri-food sector: digitalising, greening"	<p>This first international networking event took place within ETF's new project "Skilling up the Western Balkan agri-food sector: digitalising, greening" which was officially launched in June 2022. It brings together innovative SMEs in the agri-food sector, business associations, clusters and education, training and research Institutions involved in innovation, upskilling and reskilling the workforce. Together with ETF, the Turin Chamber of Commerce is a key partner for the organisation of this event which takes place under the umbrella of the Enterprise Europe Network (EEN) over a period of 2,5 days.</p>

Project Partner	Date	Name of the conference	Description
<p>ENVISION as a solution </p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> A toolbox of services for the continuous and systematic monitoring of sustainable agricultural practices, enabling monitoring organisations to adapt to requirements stemming from the EU policy reform 3 different customized solutions <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ENVISION Web Interface (PAs & CBs), ENVISION mobile app (Farmers), ENVISION Add-on Development Tool (Developers) 6 EO-based and ML-empowered products: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> 1) Cultivated Crop Type Maps, 2) Soil Organic Carbon, 3) Vegetation Status, 4) Crop Growth (distinction of organic – conventional farming), 5) Grassland Mowing/ Ploughing, 6) Soil Erosion 			<p>It was organised in partnership with the international event “Terra Madre Salone del Gusto” which brings together international players from the agri-food sector from all over the globe. During your stay in Turin, we had the opportunity to meet other participants, including SME’s, intermediary bodies and researchers in the area of agri-food with the aim to start building partnership and to learn from each other.</p> <p>InoSens representative, Vladimir Mrkajic, presented portfolio of Horizon projects in which the company participate - including the ENVISION project.</p>

2.11 PR articles published in national/regional/European press

PR articles published in national/regional/European press are important dissemination channels for sharing ENVISION results in the community.

Table 10: PR articles published in national/regional/European press

Project Partner	Date	Title of the publication	Title of the Journal	Publication document (URL)
OCS	25/02/2022	ENVISION – Monitoring ekoloških praksi za održivu poljoprivredu u zemlji (Earth Observation - EG)	Terras	https://terras.org.rs/envision-monitoring-ekoloskih-praksiza-odrzivu-poljoprivredu-uz-podrsku-posmatranja-zemlje/
ETAM	9/3/2022	Παρακολούθηση γεωργικών	Geotee.gr	https://www.geotee.gr/MainNewsDetail.aspx?CatID=1&RefID=24716&TabID=4

Project Partner	Date	Title of the publication	Title of the Journal	Publication document (URL)
		πρακτικών με τεχνολογίες δορυφορικής τηλεπισκόπησης		
		<p>Οι υπηρεσίες που θα αναπτύξει το ENVISION θα δοκιμαστούν σε πραγματικό περιβάλλον, μέχρι τον Αύγουστο του 2023 στη Λιθουανία, στην Κύπρο, στο Βέλγιο και στη Σερβία και θα αφορούν στην παρακολούθηση:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> της εφαρμογής των περιβαλλοντικών και κλιματικών απαιτήσεων της ΚΑΠ, της τήρησης των απαιτήσεων της βιολογικής γεωργίας, της κατάστασης των γεωργικών εδαφών <p>Για περισσότερες πληροφορίες σχετικά με το ENVISION μπορείτε να επικοινωνήσετε μέσω ηλεκτρονικού ταχυδρομείου info@envision-h2020.eu. Αν θέλετε να παρακολουθείτε τη διαρκή πρόοδο του έργου επισκεφτείτε την ιστοσελίδα https://envision-h2020.eu/ ή κάντε εγγραφή στο Newsletter https://envision-h2020.eu/newsletter-signup/. Μπορείτε ακόμα να ακολουθήσετε τα μέσα κοινωνικής δικτύωσης https://www.linkedin.com/company/envision-h2020/, https://twitter.com/EnvisionH2020/, και https://www.facebook.com/EnvisionH2020/</p> <p>*****</p> <p>Το ENVISION χρηματοδοτείται από το Πρόγραμμα Έρευνας και Καινοτομίας Horizon 2020 της Ευρωπαϊκής Ένωσης. Δεκατέρις εταίροι από 8 χώρες υλοποιούν τις ερευνητικές εργασίες και από την Ελλάδα συμμετέχουν η DRAXIS Περιβαλλοντική Α.Ε. (Θεσσαλονίκη), το Εθνικό Αστεροσκοπείο Αθηνών, και η ETAM Α.Ε. (Ηράκλειο).</p>		
ETAM	9/3/2022	Παρακολούθηση γεωργικών πρακτικών με τεχνολογίες δορυφορικής τηλεπισκόπησης	Agro24.gr	https://www.agro24.gr/agrotika/symvoyles/geotehnikes-symvoyles/parakolythisi-georgikon-praktikon-me-tehnologies
		<p>Πριν λίγες μέρες το ENVISION δοκιμάστηκε σε συνεργασία με το ερευνητικό έργο INIA, e-share, DIONE, BEACON και EO-WISDOGET, διεξάγοντας αξιολόγηση με όλα όσα υπάρχουν στην τεχνολογία για την υποστήριξη της Γεωργίας και της Κινητής Αγοράς της Πολιτικής. Στην εκδήλωση αυτή που της κατόρθωσε των γεωργικών εδαφών</p> <p>Για περισσότερες πληροφορίες σχετικά με το ENVISION μπορείτε να επικοινωνήσετε μέσω ηλεκτρονικού ταχυδρομείου info@envision-h2020.eu. Αν θέλετε να παρακολουθείτε τη διαρκή πρόοδο του έργου επισκεφτείτε το ενδιαφέρον περίπου 300 συμμετεχόντων από όλα την Ευρώπη, παρουσιάστηκαν όλα τα στοιχεία ερευνητικά έργα, τα κύρια αποτελέσματα και οι κοινοπραξίες τους. Το νόημα και οι προοπτικές της εκδήλωσης διαβάσαμε στην ιστοσελίδα του ENVISION https://envision-h2020.eu/earth-observation-services-in-support-of-agric...</p> <p>Οι υπηρεσίες που θα αναπτύξει το ENVISION θα δοκιμαστούν σε πραγματικό περιβάλλον, μέχρι τον Αύγουστο του 2023 στη Λιθουανία, στην Κύπρο, στο Βέλγιο και στη Σερβία και θα αφορούν στην παρακολούθηση:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> της εφαρμογής των περιβαλλοντικών και κλιματικών απαιτήσεων της ΚΑΠ, της τήρησης των απαιτήσεων της βιολογικής γεωργίας, <p>Εργία επισκεφτείτε την ιστοσελίδα https://envision-h2020.eu/ ή κάντε εγγραφή στο Newsletter https://envision-h2020.eu/newsletter-signup/. Μπορείτε ακόμα να ακολουθήσετε τα μέσα κοινωνικής δικτύωσης https://www.linkedin.com/company/envision-h2020/, https://twitter.com/EnvisionH2020/, και https://www.facebook.com/EnvisionH2020/</p> <p>Το ENVISION χρηματοδοτείται από το Πρόγραμμα Έρευνας και Καινοτομίας Horizon 2020 της Ευρωπαϊκής Ένωσης. Δεκατέρις εταίροι από 8 χώρες υλοποιούν τις ερευνητικές εργασίες και από την Ελλάδα συμμετέχουν η DRAXIS Περιβαλλοντική Α.Ε. (Θεσσαλονίκη), το Εθνικό Αστεροσκοπείο Αθηνών, και η ETAM Α.Ε. (Ηράκλειο).</p>		
ETAM	9/3/2022	Παρακολούθηση γεωργικών πρακτικών με τεχνολογίες δορυφορικής τηλεπισκόπησης	Startup.gr	https://www.startup.gr/themata/technologie-amp-epistimi/parakolythisi-georgikon-praktikonme-technologies-doryforikis-tilepiskopisis/

Project Partner	Date	Title of the publication	Title of the Journal	Publication document (URL)
ETAM	10/3/2022	Παρακολούθηση γεωργικών πρακτικών με τεχνολογίες δορυφορικής τηλεπισκόπησης	Ka-business.gr	https://kabusiness.gr/koinonia/parakolythisi-georgikon-praktikon-me-technologies-doryforikis-tilepiskopisis/
OCS	16/3/2022	Počela "Bio škola" – Trodnevna obuka o organskoj proizvodnji	Yueco.rs	https://yueco.rs/pocela-bio-skola-trodnevna-obuka-o-organskoj-proizvodnji/ https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=Phps-CfnkYg&t=759s
OCS	16/3/2022	Počea "Bio-škola" obuka iz oblasti organske proizvodnje	Vojvodanski.com	https://vojvodanski.com/tvsubotica/po-ljoprivreda/2022/05/16/pocela-bio-skola-obuka-iz-oblasti-organske-proizvodnje

Project Partner	Date	Title of the publication	Title of the Journal	Publication document (URL)
		<p>„Bio - škola“, obuka koja se odnosi na znanja iz oblasti organske proizvodnje, počela je danas na Otvorenom univerzitetu. Ovu obuku pohađaju polaznici iz Vrnjačke Banje, dok su domaćini u ulozi predavača.</p> <p>Cilj „Bio - škole“ je upoznavanje polaznika sa načinom organske proizvodnje u našim krajevima, odnosno iskustvima naših proizvođača. Među učesnicima su i predstavnici Udruženja „Seoske žene“ iz Vrnjačke Banje, a kako objašnjava njihova članica Milica Đorđević, informacije koje ovde budu dobili, primenjivaće dalje u Udruženju.</p> <p>Guesti iz Vrnjačke Banje dolazili su već nekoliko puta u naš grad, kada je reč o saradnji na temu bio - proizvodnje. S obzirom da je naše mesto jedno od turističkih centara na Balkanu, pokušavamo na mnogim poljima da poboljšamo kvalitet, pa tako i u oblasti organske proizvodnje, ističe predsednik Komisije za poljoprivredu Vrnjačka Banja, Žarko Marković.</p> <p>Sam program zamišljen je iz dva dela, odnosno iz teorijskog kao i praktičnog. Tokom trajanja obuke obilaziće se i određene farme, kako bi polaznici videli dobre primere proizvodnje i poslovanja u oblasti organske proizvodnje i u praksi.</p> <p>Predavanja realizuje udruženje Terras u saradnji sa Otvorenim univerzitetom i ona traju do 18.maja.</p>		
OCS	18/3/2022	Održana edukacija o organskoj proizvodnji u Rogatici	Katera.news	https://katera.news/lat/odrzana-edukacija-o-organskoj-proizvodnji-u-rogatici
		<p>Predstavnici Ministarstva poljoprivrede, šumarstva i vodoprivrede Republike Srpske i „Organic Control System“ d.o.o. juče su u Rogatici održali predavanje za poljoprivredne proizvođače koji su zainteresovani za sertifikaciju organske proizvodnje.</p> <p>Predavanju su prisustvovali proizvođači iz svih dvanaest opština koje pokriva Područna jedinica Sokolac Resora za pružanje stručnih usluga u poljoprivredi, saopšteno je iz ove opštine.</p> <p>Prisutni su imali priliku da se upoznaju sa značajem organske poljoprivredne proizvodnje i procedurom sertifikacije. Organska poljoprivreda podrazumeva proizvodnju u skladu sa zakonom i standardima i inspekciju cjelokupnog proizvodnog ciklusa od strane ovlašćenih organizacija.</p> <p>„Organic Control System“ je ovlašćena kontrolna organizacija koja se bavi kontrolom i sertifikacijom organske primarne biljne i životinjske proizvodnje, prerade, sakupljanja divjih biljnih vrsta, šumskih plodova i pečuraka, uvoza i prometa organskih proizvoda.</p> <p>Ministarstvo poljoprivrede, šumarstva i vodoprivrede Republike Srpske, kroz Pravilnik o podsticajima, podržava proizvođače koji imaju sertifikovanu organsku proizvodnju i proizvodnju u periodu konverzije, dodali su u saopštenju.</p> <p>Cilj organske poljoprivrede je proizvodnja hrane visokog kvaliteta, koja doprinosi očuvanju životne sredine, pravilnoj ishrani i očuvanju ljudskog zdravlja i razvoju ruralnih područja.</p>		
OCS	9/8/2022	ENVISION – Monitoring ekoloških praksi za održivu poljoprivredu u uz podršku posmatranja Zemlje	ICT cluster Vojvodina	https://vojvodinaictcluster.org/sr/envision-monitoring-ekoloskih-praksi-za-odrzivu-poljoprivredu-uz-podrsku-posmatranja-zemlje-earth-observation-eo/

Project Partner	Date	Title of the publication	Title of the Journal	Publication document (URL)
NPA	2/12/2022	ENVISION projekte kuriamos inovatyvios tvaraus ūkininkavimo stebėjimo priemonės		https://www.nma.lt/index.php/naujienos/envision-projekte-kuriamos-inovatyvios-tvaraus-ukininkavimo-stebėjimo-priemonės/44713
NPA	5/10/2022	Pirmasis projekto Horizon 2020 ENVISION susitikimas		https://www.nma.lt/index.php/naujienos/pirmasis-projekto-horizon-2020-envision-susitikimas/44713
NPA	7/2/2023	H2020 ENVISION project develops innovative monitoring tools for		https://www.nma.lt/index.php/naujienos/h2020-envision-project-develops-innovative-monitoring-tools-for-sustainable-farming/44713

Project Partner	Date	Title of the publication	Title of the Journal	Publication document (URL)
		sustainable farming		
OCS	6/10/2022	18. Međunarodni festival organskih proizvoda Biofest (Program)	Subotica.org	https://www.subotica.info/2022/10/06/18-medunarodni-festival-organskih-proizvoda-biofest-program
OCS	12/10/2022	Otvoren 18. Biofest, međunarodna manifestacija posvećena organskim proizvodima	Subotica.com	https://www.subotica.com/vesti/otvore-n-18-biofest-medunarodna-manifestacija-posvecena-organskim-proizvodima-id45213.html

Project Partner	Date	Title of the publication	Title of the Journal	Publication document (URL)
		<p>Otvoren 18. "Biofest", međunarodna manifestacija posvećena organskim proizvodima</p> <p>Medunarodna manifestacija posvećena organskoj proizvodnji okupila je uzemke i štogare iz Srbije, Republike Srbije i Hrvatske.</p> <p>NOVA GENERACIJA ORGANSKIH FARMERA A NEW GENERATION OF ORGANIC FARMERS</p> <p>18. BIOFEST MEĐUNARODNA MANIFESTACIJA POSVEĆENA ORGANSKOJ PROIZVODNJI INTERNATIONAL ORGANIC FOOD FESTIVAL</p>		<p>U Otvorenu 18. izdanja "Biofesta" je digitalizacija u organskoj poljoprivredi. Otvoreni ovogodišnji "Biofest" je "Nova generacija organskih farmera" a želimo mladim proizvođačima da ukažemo na značaj digitalne pismenosti, jer moderna tehnologija i digitalizacija preuzimaju veliku ulogu u organskoj poljoprivrednoj proizvodnji. Na jednom od panela bude prikazano i kako funkcionise jedna digitalna farma - obilježava Sređana Mitrović, organizatorica "Biofesta". Cilj nam je i da edukujemo naše sugrađane kako da prepoznaju organski proizvod koji mora imati prepoznatljiv znak bilo da je domaći ili uvoze.</p> <p>Organska poljoprivredna proizvodnja iz godine u godinu je sve prisutnija, a razlog za to su bezbedni i zdravstveno ispravni proizvodi, kao i očuvanje životne sredine što je imperativ za održivost poljoprivrede. Istakao je Mladen Petreš, pomoćnik pokrajinskog sekretara za poljoprivredu.</p> <p>Pokrajinski sekretarjat preporučuje te tendencije i u skladom je kontaktu sa organskim proizvođačima. U skladu sa tim ove godine prilagodili smo naše mere potrebama poljoprivrednika koji se bave organskom proizvodnjom i povećali unos sredstava koje mogu dobiti na konkurenciju kako za nabavu opreme i mehanizacije, tako i za sertifikaciju - kazao je Petreš i dodao je u Vijestima oko 8 hiljada hektara pod organskom proizvodnjom.</p> <p>Priznanje "organski proizvod godine" u okviru ovogodišnjeg "Biofesta" pripalo je domaćim farmari dečje hrane sa proizvod "Nutriom organski", dok je priznanje "organski proizvod godine" pripalo Saraj Kuzmanović u Čemju.</p> <p>Održavajući svojeve roštilje koji su nam sugerišali da za svoje bebe želi hranu pripremljenu od domaćih organskih proizvoda, bez aditiva i konzervansa krevali smo fest "Nutriom organski" proizvoda a do kraja godine na roštilje ćemo plasirati još četiri - poručuje Jelena Bilić iz ove farme dečje hrane - "Organicni proizvodom je bismo od 2019. godine, koji naj je najblijem zastupljenom povrtarstvu, a od ove godine počeli smo i sa karabostrom. Imamo i manje začine vode. Ove organske poljoprivredne mlade proizvođače da se divi, počeli smo sa 6,8 hektara, a sada radimo na 3,5 hektara i imamo oko 3.200 kvadrata pod plastenicima - nadovezuje se odbornica priznanja "organski proizvod godine".</p> <p>U okviru 18. izdanja "Biofesta" u holu Otvorenog univerziteta upriličena je izložba bio proizvoda koju možete pogledati danas do 18h, kao i sutra od 10 do 18h.</p>
OCS	12/10/2022	U Subotici JE DANAS otvoren "Biofest": Ukusni organski proizvodi in najsvežije povrće!	Espresso.co.rs	https://www.espresso.co.rs/vesti/drustvo/1156601/u-subotici-je-danas-otvoren-biofest-ukusni-organski-proizvodi-i-najsvezije-povrce-video
		<p>OTVORENI UNIVERZITET</p> <p>U SUBOTICI JE DANAS OTVOREN "BIOFEST": Ukusni organski proizvodi i najsvežije povrće! (VIDEO)</p> <p>Festival organskih proizvoda "BIOFEST" traje do 19. oktobra, a u okviru samog festivala održava se i panel diskusija na temu „Digitalizacijom do povećanja ekonomske, ekološke i socijalne održivosti poljoprivrede“, kao i degustacija organske dečje hrane</p> <p>Održano: 12.10.2022. 15:50h</p> <p>Festival organskih proizvoda "BIOFEST", otvoren je danas na Otvorenom univerzitetu u Subotici. Na 18. po redu festivalu organskih proizvoda, svoje proizvode prikazali su proizvođači iz Srbije, Hrvatske i Republike Srbije, a posetioši su na licu mesta imali priliku da degustiraju ukusne organske proizvode poput sokova i meda i da kupe najsvežije povrće! U organizaciji Sređanom Mitrović sa Otvorenog univerziteta u Subotici, saznali smo detalje sa ovogodišnjeg festivala.</p>		<p>Uspeli su spasiti i drugi koronavirus i to što smo organizovali 18. Međunarodni festival organskih proizvoda "Biofest". Sve sreće bi bilo moguće bez podrške mnogim organizacijama i Gradske uprave kao i Hrvatske organizacije GZ. Cilj festivala je da se ukusni organski proizvodi, da se osvrne na njihovu ulogu u zaštiti i poboljšanje kvaliteta života. Ove godine sa nama su proizvođači iz Srbije, Hrvatske i Republike Srbije, a nama je najvažnije da ovom prilikom predstavimo prepoznatljive kako da prepoznaju organski proizvod, da im mora imati sertifikaciju, da mora imati znak i obrnuto i imati etiketu koja je na primer iz Gradske uprave. Takođe imamo izložbu i u vidu generacije. Ključni generacija je ta koja ima veliku ulogu da uspe u organskoj proizvodnji. U okviru Biofesta prikazujemo ekološke dokumentarne filmove kako bi našim gledaocima, a u program smo uključili i tematsko-ekološki izložbu. Otvoreni su predstavnici svoje kulturne svesnosti, a obeležili smo im organske proizvode "Kvalita je Sređana Mitrović sa Otvorenog univerziteta u Subotici, sa Subotici.ba.</p>
		<p>Festival organskih proizvoda "BIOFEST" traje do 19. oktobra, a u okviru samog festivala održava se i panel diskusija na temu „Digitalizacijom do povećanja ekonomske, ekološke i socijalne održivosti poljoprivrede“, kao i degustacija organske dečje hrane.</p>		<p>Festival organskih proizvoda "BIOFEST" traje do 19. oktobra, a u okviru samog festivala održava se i panel diskusija na temu „Digitalizacijom do povećanja ekonomske, ekološke i socijalne održivosti poljoprivrede“, kao i degustacija organske dečje hrane.</p>
OCS	12/10/2022	Međunarodn i festival "Biofest", 18. Put, sada u	Poljosfera.rs	https://www.poljosfera.rs/agrosfera/saznajte/dogadaji/biofest/

Project Partner	Date	Title of the publication	Title of the Journal	Publication document (URL)
		znanu modernih tehnologija		
		<p>Medunarodni festival „Biofest“, 18. put, znanu u modernih tehnologija</p>		<p>„Biofest“, međunarodna manifestacija posvećena organskoj proizvodnji okupila je učesnike i organizatore iz Srbije, Republike Srbije i Slovenije.</p> <p>U okviru 18. izdanja „Biofest“ je digitalizacija u organskoj poljoprivredi. Slagan ovogodišnjeg „Biofesta“ je „Mlada generacija organskih farmara“, prenosi subotička.com.</p> <p>„Jedino mlađim proizvođačima da uštedimo na značaj digitalne pametnosti, jer modernu tehnologiju i digitalizaciju proizvodnji posebno primeni u organskoj poljoprivrednoj proizvodnji. Na jednom od panela biće prikazano i kako funkcioniše jedna digitalna ferma – odgojno-izobrazna Digitalna Mladost, organizaciona „Biofest“ – cilj nam je i da uključimo naše sugrađane kako da prepoznaju organski proizvod koji mora imati prepoznatljiv znak bilo da je domaći ili iz inostrana.</p> <p>Organska poljoprivredna proizvodnja iz godine u godinu je sve prisutnija, a razlog za to su bezbedni i zdravstveno ispravni proizvodi, kao i obnavljanje životne sredine što je imperativ za održivu poljoprivredu. Istakao je Mladen Peretić pomoćnik pokrajinskog sekretara za poljoprivredu.</p> <p>„Prilagodljivi odabirima proizvodnje se trendiraju i u stacionu je konstanta su organskim proizvodima. U skladu sa tim ove godine prilagodili smo naše mere potrebama poljoprivrednika koji se bave organskom proizvodnjom i povećali iznos sredstava koje imamo dobivenih konstantno kako za nabavku opreme i tehnologije, tako za sertifikacije – kazao je Peretić i dodao je u videozapis ološ Brijunić hlebom pod organskom proizvodnjom.</p> <p>Priznanje „organski proizvod godine“ u okviru ovogodišnjeg „Biofesta“, priprema je domaćoj fabrici dečije hrane za proizvodi „Nutrimo organik“ dok je priznanje „organski proizvod godine“ pripalo Sanji Kuzmanović iz Červinje.</p>
OCS	12/10/2022	18. Biofest u sredu i četvrtak		https://yueco.rs/18-biofest-u-sredu-i-cetvrtak/
OCS	12/10/2022	Festival organskih proizvoda Biofest otvoren u Subotici: Mlađa generacija ima više izgleda da uspe u organskoj proizvodnji!	Kurir.rs	https://www.kurir.rs/vesti/4029477/festival-organskih-proizvoda-biofest-otvoren-je-danas-na-otvorenom/media/55471

Networking

ENVISION is networking with other projects related to Earth Observation with the aim of how their solutions could contribute to ENVISION and how complementary these products are to ENVISION.

Wikifarmer

Wikifarmer is a worldwide collaboration with the mission of empowering and educating farmers across the world. It is an Organization with Social Impact, leading a transformation in Agriculture and Food Systems by focusing on free Education, Sustainability, and forcing Transparency, Accountability, Security, and Honesty, across the food supply chain. To accomplish that, Wikifarmer offers an open Library with educational material covering a wide range of agricultural topics, translated into numerous languages (more than 14), to be accessible to everyone and help farmers make fact-based decisions on how to produce sustainably high-quality products. In 2021 more than 5 million unique visitors from more than 180 countries have read our material online. At the same time, we believe that all farmers in the world should be able to showcase their production, set a price for their products, and compete fairly in the local or the global marketplace. To strengthen farmers' position in today's competitive landscape, we introduce them to e-commerce, help them create a profile online, present and translate their products and match them with buyers. Our Market Place is accessible to all farmers and buyers (for B2B and B2C transactions) worldwide and is translated into 5 languages (English, Spanish, Italian, French, and Greek).

Figure 21: Wikifarmer

2.12 Scientific and Technical publications

Scientific and technical publications are a cornerstone of the dissemination of any research project. Here, the detailed description of new ideas, concepts, methods, algorithms, tools and their experimental evaluation are disseminated in concise papers to carefully selected and focused scientific communities. Until today NOA published four publications that are listed below.

Table 11: First Scientific and Technical publication

Title of the publication	A Satellite Datacube and Crowdsourced Street-Level Images for the Monitoring of the Common Agricultural Policy
Authors	Sitokonstantinou, V., Koukos, A., Drivas, T., Kontoes, C., and Karathanassi, V.
Title of the Journal / Proceedings / Book	In International Conference on Multimedia Modeling (pp. 473-478). Springer.
DOI (Digital Object Identifier)	https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-030-98355-0_41
Publication document (URL)	https://link.springer.com/chapter/10.1007/978-3-030-98355-0_41
Number or date of the Journal /	15/3/2022

Proceedings / Book	
Relevant pages (from - to)	473-378
ISBN	978-3-030-98355-0
Publisher	© 2022 Springer Nature Switzerland AG

Table 12: Second Scientific and Technical publication

Title of the publication	A Data Cube of Big Satellite Image Time-Series for Agriculture Monitoring
Authors	Drivas, T., Sitokonstantinou, V., Tsardanidis, I., Koukos, A.,
Title of the Journal / Proceedings / Book	Computer Vision and Pattern Recognition (cs.CV); Databases (cs.DB); Multimedia (cs.MM)
DOI (Digital Object Identifier)	https://doi.org/10.48550/arXiv.2205.07752
Publication document (URL)	https://doi.org/10.48550/arXiv.2205.07752
Number or date of the Journal / Proceedings / Book	16/5/20222

Table 13: Third Scientific and Technical publication

Title of the publication	A Data Cube of Big Satellite Image Time-Series for Agriculture Monitoring
Authors	Sitokonstantinou, V., Koukos, A., Drivas, T., Kontoes, C., and Karathanassi, V.
Title of the Journal / Proceedings / Book	This work has been accepted for publication in IEEE 14th Image, Video, and Multidimensional Signal Processing Workshop (IVMSP 2022)
DOI (Digital Object Identifier)	https://doi.org/10.48550/arXiv.2205.07752
Publication document (URL)	https://arxiv.org/abs/2205.07752
Number or date of the Journal / Proceedings / Book	27/6/2022

Table 14: Fourth Scientific and Technical publication

Title of the publication	Assessing the Added Value of Sentinel-1 PoISAR Data for Crop Classification
Authors	Authors: Maria Ioannidou, Alkiviadis Koukos, Vasileios Sitokonstantino, Ioannis Papoutsis and Charalampos Kontoes
Title of the Journal / Proceedings / Book	Journal: MDPI Remote Sensing
DOI (Digital Object Identifier)	https://doi.org/10.3390/rs14225739
Publication document (URL)	https://doi.org/10.3390/rs14225739
Number or date of the Journal / Proceedings / Book	13/11/2022

2.13 White papers and Testimonials

As per task description, the project shall provide white papers and testimonials.

A white paper is a report or guide that informs readers concisely about a complex issue and presents the issuing body's philosophy on the matter. It is meant to help readers understand an issue, solve a problem, or make a decision.

A testimonial is effectively a review or recommendation from a client/target group, letting others know how the products or service benefitted them. Testimonials can be:

- Quote testimonial: This testimonial uses words directly from a satisfied customer and is the most common kind.
- Video testimonial: This testimonial is when you record your customer talking about your product. It's eye-catching, authentic and engaging.
- Interview testimonial: This testimonial uses a question-and-answer format on video or in print where you ask your customers about their experience with your company.

The guidelines for white papers and testimonials have been prepared by ITC.

First White paper was prepared by NOA:

<https://envision-h2020.eu/envision-1-white-paper-cultivated-crop-type-maps-national-observatory-of-athens/>

National Observatory of Athens

CULTIVATED CROP TYPE MAPS

Contact
Haris Kontoes

Email
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Transform your agriculture practices with our innovative Cultivated Crop Type Maps service. Our service combines advanced satellite data and Machine Learning techniques to classify crops accurately and validate the declared crop types by farmers. With our product, Paying Agencies and Certification Bodies can enhance their inspection processes during both the declaration and validation stages to promote sustainable agricultural practices, increase food security, and facilitate subsidy allocations. Our accurate crop classification maps are provided throughout the cultivation period, providing a powerful monitoring tool that contributes to the overall growth and development of the agricultural sector.

Experience the power of our technology and revolutionize your agriculture management with our creative solution!

KEY FEATURES:

- Dynamic Crop Type Maps**
The service provides multiple crop type maps at a national scale throughout the cultivation period, generated by new or groups of new Sentinel acquisitions. This provides an up-to-date and accurate monitoring tool for agriculture management, allowing for optimal decision-making throughout the cultivation period.
- Alert Mechanism**
Our advanced smart sampling algorithm uses a traffic light system to detect potential instances of false applicant declarations, even in the initial stages of the cultivation period. This helps to reduce fraud and errors in crop reporting, ensuring accurate data for subsidies and other financial programs.
- Supervision of Cross-Compliance**
The results derived from the Cultivated Crop Type Maps service serve as the foundation for addressing Greening requirements, such as Crops Diversification, making it a vital tool for anyone seeking to optimize the monitoring of farming operations. This feature helps to ensure compliance with regulations and promote sustainable agricultural practices.
- Improved Inspection Processes**
With accurate crop classification maps provided throughout the cultivation period, the service offers a valuable solution to Paying Agencies and Certification Bodies seeking to enhance their inspection processes.

The ENVISION project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 869366.

**White
paper**

PAS ADVANTAGES WITH CULTIVATED CROP TYPE MAPS:

-
Scalability
 Our system is designed to provide accurate crop classification results at any scale, from a small Area of Interest to an entire country.

-
Generalization Performance
 Our service provides reliable crop classification information across different regions, helping Paying Agencies to make informed decisions about agriculture management strategies. Paying Agencies can manage diverse regions with varying crops and cultivation practices.

-
Cloud Coverage Resilient
 Our service employs both Sentinel-1 and Sentinel-2 data to ensure higher accuracy and address the issues of extended cloud coverage and the impact of weather condition on data collection.

-
Cost Reduction
 Inspections can be carried out more efficiently, reducing the need for costly manual field visits. Paying Agencies can save time and resources, and focus on other critical tasks related to agriculture management.

Crops Classification Map based on declaration polygons, describing each crop category with different colors

The ENVISION project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 869366.

**White
paper**

WHAT OUR CUSTOMER SAY:

"Cultivated Crop Type Maps has helped us identify key areas of concern regarding farmer's declarations, as well as tackle significant challenges pertaining to the natural characteristics of plots in Cyprus. Sophisticated approaches to data analytics and the adjustability of the service have allowed for increased accuracy, timely alerts, and useful guidance to CAPO for selecting and focusing on high-risk areas or crop groups. Either directly integrated or acting complementary, it definitely is a high-value product."

CAPO – Cyprus Payment Organizations

For more information, visit <https://envision-h2020.eu/>
and follow us on social media:

 [ENVISIONH2020](#)

 [ENVISIONH2020](#)

The ENVISION project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 869366.

Figure 22: First White Paper provided by NOA

OCS prepared the first video testimonial, and it was published on ENVISION YouTube channel: <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=my7dl7h4vs4>

2.14 Meetings with PA, CB, Farm Associations, EO companies/institutions, EU institutions

All partners focus on building up trust and cooperation with PA, CB, Farm Associations, EO companies/institutions, EU institutions. Among other actions, we are arranging meetings to introduce the project initially. We will keep this constant relationship alive throughout the lifespan of the whole project.

Table 15: Meetings with PA, CB, Farm Associations, EO companies/institutions, EU institutions

Project Partner	Date	Organisation/Meeting name	Meeting description
OCS	17/3/2022	Inspection and certification of organic production	<p>Presentation way of inspection and certification of organic production. At the end of the meeting, OCS presented what is ENVISION and what will be benefits in the future from this project.</p>
OCS	18/3/2022	Inspection and certification of organic production	
NPA	30/3/2022	Future CAP and innovative tools to overcome the emerging challenges	The aim of the meeting was to review the innovative tools under development within the scope of Horizon 2020 projects with the participation of the NPA as well as to

Project Partner	Date	Organisation/Meting name	Meeting description
			<p>summarize the upcoming challenges of the CAP 2023-2027. The respective Horizon 2020 projects were presented, alongside the test results and the current version of NIVA tools, and how these tools could be implemented in the future in line with other tools from NPA projects such as DIONE, ENVISION and EIFFEL. IACS and GIS experts from central office and inspectors from regional offices agreed that digital innovations from the projects could reduce administrative burden and speed up payments to the farmers.</p> <p>During live demo session UC2 preliminary parcels boundaries' results were shown on screen with possible usage examples. Also, early stage crop classification was presented and demonstrated based on Sen4CAP results alongside robotized workflow to capture data from state forest service webpage to NPA data base. Meeting participants discussed UC2 deployment achievements, improvements and priorities for final phase, and it was agreed for 2022 claim year to run algorithm by using 1 m deep resolve Sentinel 2 image as input data. Generated results will be uploaded into "NMA agro" mobile app as an additional layer.</p> <p>All NIVA tools are very interesting and useful so according to NPA preparation strategy for future CAP it was agreed to focus on LPIS automated update tool, geotagged photos automated recognition with AI and agro-environmental monitoring. Finally, recommendations about NIVA tools will be shared with other companies included in IACS process.</p>
ITC	8/4/2022	Farm manager Kick-off meeting - meeting with Public advisory service	The meeting has been organised under the umbrella of Farm manager Kick-off meeting. The Farm manager is the platform

Project Partner	Date	Organisation/Meting name	Meeting description
			<p>developed by the ITC and Institute of Agriculture Murska Sobota and is to be used by Slovenian advisors and farmers in the future. The platform is providing EO services (Indexes) in order to support advisors/farmers in following their land, while the meeting was used to gather information and needs from advisors/farmers in case of specific EO services provided from ENVISION project.</p> <p>Attendance:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - ITC staff and developers - Institute of Agriculture (representatives from 8 regional offices/institutes) <p>The meeting resulted in positive feedback from the advisors about the future use of EO services, especially they were interested in:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Cultivated crop type maps: to be able to allow a quick overview of specific business planning input data (real-time and historic identification of cultivation per specific land parcel) - Analysis on vegetation and soil index time series: to support farmers in comparing vegetation indexes and provide initial insight into the full scale service - DSS - Soil organic carbon monitoring: in order to allow quick overview of land parcels and precision farming techniques implemented by advanced farmers.
OCS	16/5/2022	BIO SCHOOL	<p>Presentation way of inspection and certification of organic production. At the end of the meeting, OCS presented what is ENVISION and what will be benefits in the future from this project.</p>
OCS	28/6/2022	Trainig about new EU regulation for organic production	<p>New import procedures into the EU from 1/1/22, recognition process for compliant certification bodies, how to recognize and</p>

Project Partner	Date	Organisation/Meting name	Meeting description
			<p>define non-conformity thru the organic inspection. In the meeting, OCS presented what is ENVISION and what will be the benefits in the future from this project.</p>
NPA	14/7/2022	Polish Agency for Restructuring and Modernization of Agriculture (ARMA)	<p>On July 13-14th a meeting between the experts of the National Paying Agency (NPA) and the Polish Agency for Restructuring and Modernization of Agriculture (ARMA) took place in the NPA headquarters in Vilnius. During the meeting, the support administration system, the strategy for the new programming period 2023-2027 were discussed, as well as the newly implemented field monitoring system was presented by NPA specialists.</p> <p>Discussions during the meeting focused on the implementation of the support measures foreseen in the Strategic Plan for Agriculture and Rural Development of Lithuania 2023-2027 as well as necessary preparatory actions for its implementation.</p> <p>Good practices in support administration were also shared and other topics were discussed, such as crop and plant insurance premium reimbursement measures applied in Lithuania, state aid measures, administration of direct payments. The NMA Agro mobile app as well as the new monitoring tool – Automatic continuous field monitoring system (ALNSIS) – were presented.</p> <p>Prospects of further collaboration between NPA (Lithuania) and ARMA (Poland) were discussed, as well as the possible topics of the forthcoming conference of the Baltic States and Poland.</p>
NPA	11/8/2022	Introduction to ALNSIS	<p>A presentation about the Automated Permanent Field Monitoring System (ALNSIS) – a Lithuanian version of the Area Monitoring System (AMS), specified by the EC as obligatory in the forthcoming</p>

Project Partner	Date	Organisation/Meeting name	Meeting description
			<p>programming period – was delivered by the representative of the NPA Control Department Aušrius Kučinskis to the wide audience of the NPA.</p> <p>Firstly, Automated Permanent Field Monitoring System (ALNSIS) will allow to identify dishonest applicants and reallocate the financial support to the honest ones. Secondly, the NPA will give an early warning of potential irregularities or discrepancies in the agricultural / farming areas. At this stage the farmer becomes a proactive participant of the process and he may have a final influence on his payment by performing appropriate actions. Algorithms are the ALNSIS main driver; and currently we have 24 ALNSIS algorithms: 4 land cover algorithms that we use for monitoring the whole territory of Lithuania: arable land, grasslands, permanent crops, non-eligible land plots, whereas there is also a mowing algorithm in place. Aiming to facilitate the work for farmers, we have developed the mobile “NPA Agro” application.</p>
NPA	24/8/2022	Visit from the Latvian Paying Agency	<p>On 24 August colleagues from the Latvian Paying Agency, Rural Support Service, visited the National Paying Agency under the Ministry of Agriculture (NPA). In the open discussion the challenges that the NPA faces in preparation for the new programming period were presented, as well as measures that have been taken to tackle them. The work model of the NPA was also discussed, including the approach of evaluating the NPA performance results, structural changes foreseen in the new period.</p> <p>The guests from Latvia familiarised themselves with the technological innovations that have been implemented, including introduction of the Area Monitoring System.</p> <p>Colleagues not only gained knowledge and found out about good practices, but also</p>
<div data-bbox="220 1451 805 1579"> <p>2022.08.26</p> <p>Visit from the Latvian Paying Agency</p> <p><small>On 24 August colleagues from the Latvian Paying Agency, Rural Support Service, visited the National Paying Agency under the Ministry of Agriculture (NPA). In the open discussion the challenges that the NPA faces in preparation for the new programming period were presented, as well as measures that have been taken to tackle them. The work model of the NPA was also discussed, including the approach of evaluating the NPA performance results, structural changes foreseen in the new period. The guests from Latvia familiarised themselves with the technological innovations that have been implemented, including introduction of the Area Monitoring System.</small></p> </div>			

Project Partner	Date	Organisation/Meeting name	Meeting description
			<p>shared information about their agency's preparatory work for the transition period. After the meeting, the representatives of both agencies highlighted the benefits of the bilateral cooperation and expressed hope that such meetings will be held also in the future.</p>
INOS 	12/9/2022	26th MARS Conference	<p>The MARS conference brought together the community of technical experts in the domain of administration and control of the area based subsidy schemes. It covered the technologies, methods and protocols that bring effectiveness and efficiency to that domain. Participation was open to experts from administrations, industry, academic and research institutions.</p> <p>The themes addressed were built on the paradigm shift between the past delivery model based on compliance to a new delivery model based on performance. The agenda contained the following sessions:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - The state of Copernicus based technology, - The CAP new delivery and management model, - IACS data management processes (including QA), - Introducing Performance towards Environmental and Climate targets, - Technical community developments (e.g. geotagged imagery, artificial intelligence, H2020 project outcomes, beneficiary interaction and other) -The paradigm shift: end of an era: lessons learnt from the compliance model -Using new technologies: driving the paradigm shift -The 2023+ CAP: requirements, instruments and challenges -The environmental ambition: the performance targets -The land ahead: information on the management of land

Project Partner	Date	Organisation/Meting name	Meeting description
			<p>During the conference social events where attendees had a chance to meet and discuss, Inosens used a chance to introduce the Envision project in general and InoSens work in particular to various stakeholders, including Paying Agency representatives but also EO technology providers.</p> <p>The ENVISION project is dealing with very "hot" topics and its outcomes and results are of interest to both paying agencies and EO technology providers.</p>
NOA	15/9/2022	ENVISION Earth Observation Services demonstration to LV Flanders	NOA presented briefly its' ENVISION EO services developed to LV Flanders
INOS	19/4/2022	8th General Assembly of WATERAGRI Project (H2020)	<p>The event brings together experts from various fields to share an update on water retention and nutrient recovery solutions development within the framework of WATERAGRI project (H2020). With a focus on addressing global challenges, General Assembly Meeting highlight the future goals and tasks of the WATERAGRI consortium partners.</p> <p>Inosens used this opportunity to several informal person-to-person meeting with stakeholders from agriculture (such as networking organizations, farmers) to inform them about InoSens activities and ongoing projects. Here, Inosens informed them about Envision project and its activities and achievements, as well as</p>

4 Analysis of results

The table below presents the Key Performance Indicators (KPI) used to evaluate the performance of the project's actions. To reach those KPIs, the Consortium is constantly working. As showcased in this table, some KPIs are already achieved, and some are in good way to be achieved in the next last few months of the project.

Table 16: Key Performance Indicators

Number and name	Indicator	Target value	Achieved from the beginning of the project until the end of this period
C1 Envision website	Numbers of visits to the project website	10.000	6576
C2 A commercial mini-site	A commercial mini-site	1	0
C3 Social Media (Twitter, LinkedIn, Facebook, YouTube, SlideShare)	Followers on Social Media	1.200	719
	Posts on social networks relevant to the project	1.200	372
C4 Animation video	Animation video	1	2
C5 ENVISION e-Newsletters	Recipients of project e-newsletters	5.000	50 Mailchimp 504 ENVISION social media 2412 DIH Social Media
C6 ENVISION promotional material	Brochure and leaflets	3.000	1620 printed leaflets
	Roll-up and poster	1 and 1	1 and 1
C7 EuroGEOSS showcase	Expression of interest signed by EuroGEOSS and ENVISION LP	1	1
C8 Hackathon	Hackathon	1	0
C9 Meetings with developers, open-source communities	Meetings with developers, open-source communities	10	6
C10 Informal person-to-person meetings with stakeholders	Informal person-to-person meetings with stakeholders	80	14
C11 Policy session	Policy session	1	1
C12 Project events (seminars/workshops)	Project events	8	3
C13 Clustering events/workshops	Clustering events/workshops	2	1
C14 External events	External events	15	10
C15 Presentation/attending at International Conferences	Presentation/attending at International Conferences	20	7

Number and name	Indicator	Target value	Achieved from the beginning of the project until the end of this period
C16 PR articles published in national/regional/European press	PR articles published in national/regional/European press	100	7
C17 Publications in business journals	Publications in business journals	10	1
C18 Scientific and Technical publications	Publication	3	0
C19 White papers and testimonials	White papers and testimonials	6 White papers and 13 testimonials	1 and 1
C20 Meetings with PA, CB, Farm Associations, EO companies/institutions, EU institutions	Meetings with PA, CB, Farm Associations, EO companies/institutions, EU institutions	40	26

5 Conclusions and next steps

The WP7 leader and all project partners implemented the respective dissemination and communication strategy during this reporting period with a clear focus on achieving the final goal of successful project dissemination, promotion and communication. The range of partners in the ENVISION project gives an added potential for the dissemination of the project results, enhancing successful exploitation.

According to the Dissemination and Communication plan, the goal of this reporting period was to create a more targeted awareness regarding techniques towards researchers, industry key players and stakeholders, relevant industry associations and local communities, and engage farmers who will provide data.

This document defines the draft report on dissemination activities and provides a review and analysis of all dissemination and communication tasks from March 2022.

During the third phase (M35 – M39), the aim is to focus on the promotion of concrete results to key stakeholders and potential customers.

The most ambitious goal, and for which all above mentioned and performed actions contribute, is to spread ENVISION activities effectively, achievements, and tangible results to targeted audiences, also becoming the cornerstone for the successful commercialization and market uptake of ENVISION toolbox.

Next steps:

- Focused publications of success stories, lessons learnt, standardisation activities

- 5th e-newsletter
- Social media posts
- Conferences
- Workshops
- Events
- White papers and testimonials
- ENVISION Clustering Event will be held on – 30. 6. 2023 and the following projects/ groups will participate and talk about “Solutions to support the current and the future needs of CAP monitoring and agriculture sustainability in general; presentation and discussion”:
 - ENVISION
 - CALLISTO
 - AGRIBITI
 - SPACE4GREEN
 - VITIGEOSS
 - EUROGEOS Agriculture Action Group
- Hackathon will be held in November 2023 within the conference BiDS (Big Data from Space 2023)

End of Document

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